

Contributions to Coreoidea (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) fauna of Kayseri Province (Turkey)

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ABSTRACT: 159 Coreoidea specimens were collected for identification during the expedition which made between June-August 2011-2012 in Yahyalı district (Kayseri province). The result of the identification process; 16 genera and 24 species were found belonging to 4 families. Information about the location of the studied area and Heteroptera fauna were reported in the search. Examination materials were arranged for each species with the necessary collecting data. The distribution of species were also considered in Turkey. In the results of the search references, all of 24 species are new record for Coreoidea fauna of Yahyalı.

KEYWORDS: Kayseri, Fauna, Coreoidea (Heteroptera), Turkey

To cite this article: Kiyak, S., Baş, A., 2020, Contributions to Coreoidea (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) fauna of Kayseri Province (Turkey), *J.Het.Turk.*, 2 (1):25-33

To link to this article: <https://www.j-ht.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/V21-A4.pdf>

Received: March 27, 2020; **Revised:** April 17, 2020; **Accepted:** April 25, 2020; **Published online:** May 7, 2020

INTRODUCTION

According to Dolling (1996), there are 462 species/subspecies taxa of 125 genera of 4 families (Alydidae, Coreidae, Stenocephalidae and Rhopalidae) belonging to the superfamily of Coreoidea (Hemiptera: Heteroptera) in the Palearctic region.

The superfamily Coreoidea are represented 94 species/subspecies and 36 genera belonging

to 4 family (Alydidae, Coreidae, Stenocephalidae and Rhopalidae) in Turkey. Their numerical distribution is Alydidae: 4 genera, 7 species, Coreidae: 20 genera, 48 species, Stenocephalidae: 1 genus, 7 species and Rhopalidae: 11 genera, 29 species (Fent and Dursun, 2019).

In recent years, Fent and Dursun, who are Turkish researchers, have important works on Coreoidea. Some these studies

are Dursun (2009, 2011), Dursun & Fent (2009), Dursun et al. (2010); Dursun & Fent (2015) and Fent and Dursun (2019) and Zengin & Dursun (2019).

There is no study until now about Yahyalı Heteroptera fauna. In this study, the fauna of the Coreoidea of Yahyalı surrounding (Kayseri/Turkey) was investigated and the distribution, habitat and host plants of the species were given.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Yahyalı, which is a research area, is located on the east-facing slopes of the Sakız Mountain, which surrounds the Sultan Marshes in the south of Erciyes Mountain in the south of Kayseri province. It is located in the south of Yeşilhisar bounded with the district of Aladağlar protection zone status.

The continental climate prevails in the study area. There are fertile and partly

damaged forest areas in the area. At the foot of the mountains, there are orchards, vineyards, cultivated areas, meadows and pastures, and arable areas. The plains are covered with steppe plants. Zamantı River, Kapuzbaşı Waterfalls, Derebağ Waterfalls and Kocaçay rivers passing through Yahyalı borders, which are approximately 1210 meters in altitude, are the main rivers. Naturally, the dominant character of vegetation is stepp formation. Forest formation *Pinus nigra*, *Populus* sp. species.

The material discussed in this study was collected from 10 different locations between 2011 and 2012 in Yahyalı and its vicinity (Kayseri) (Figure 1, Table 1). The samples were collected on plants with the help of sweep net.

The samples were determined using identification keys by Stichel (1957-1962), Kerzhner & Yachevskii (1964) Pehlivan (1981), Moullet (1985) and Kıyak (1990).

Figure.1- Sampling locations (●) in the study area in Yahyalı (Kayseri/Turkey).

The following literature was used for the valid taxon name and the distribution of species in Turkey (Alkan, 1948; Hoberlandt, 1955; Seidenstücker, 1957, 1958, 1960; Stichel, 1957; Tuatay et al., 1972; Zümreoğlu, 1972; Altınayar, 1981; Pehlivan, 1981; Moulet, 1985; Kiyak, 1990a,b,c, 1993; Kiyak & Çağlar, 1991; Çağlar, 1992; Özsarac & Kiyak, 2001; Özsarac, 2004; Önder et al., 2006; Dursun & Fent, 2009, 2015; Dursun et al., 2010; Kment & Banar, 2010; Çerçi et al., 2018; Fent & Dursun, 2019; Zengin & Dursun, 2019; Dursun, 2015, 2019)

RESULTS

In this study, 16 genera and 24 species belonging to 4 families of Coreoidea superfamily are given.

In total, 4 species Alydidae (2 genera), 10 species of Coreidae (7 genera), 9 species of Rhopalidae (6 genera), and 1 species of Stenocephalidae (1 genus) are listed as the fauna of Yahyalı surrounding of Kayseri province.

The list of species and geographical distribution of Turkey are given below.

Alydidae Amyot & Serville, 1843

Alydus calcaratus (Linne, 1758)

Material examined: 1 ♀, 15.07.2011 (locality 1), 1 ♀, 07.08.2012 (locality 10).

Habitat: Specimens belonging to the species were found in *Pinus nigra* forest formation, grassy steppes and Gramineae at an altitude of 1249 m and 1376 m.

Camptopus tragacanthae (Kolenati, 1845)

Material examined: 2 ♀♀, 21.06.2011 (locality 1), 2 ♀♀, 08.08.2012 (locality 10), 4 ♀♀, 27.09.2011 (locality 6), 3 ♂♂, 22.06.2011 (locality 5), 1 ♂, 13.07.2011 (locality 2).

Habitat: Examples of the species were found at herbaceous steppe formations, *Pinus nigra* forest formation *Astragalus* spp. and *Onobrychis* sp. 1249 m, 1174 m, 1376 m, 1548 m, 1507 m were observed.

Camptopus lateralis (Germar, 1817)

Material examined: 5♂♂, 05.09.2011, 4 ♀♀, 13.06.2011 (locality 1), 3 ♂♂, 06.08.2012 (locality 10), 2 ♀♀, 27.08.2011 (locality 6), 2♀♀, 28.07.2011 (locality 2).

Habitat: Examples of the species were found at an altitude of 1249 m, 1174 m, 1507 m and 1376 m from the *Pinus nigra* forest formation, herbaceous steppe, the region where the crop plants dominate and the fields.

Camptopus illustris Horvath, 1899

Material examined: 1 ♂, 15.07.2011 (locality 1), 1 ♀, 25.08.2011 (locality 1), 1 ♀, 25.06.2011 (locality 4)

Habitat: Samples of the species were found in *Pinus nigra* forest formation and 1249 m and 1450 m in grassy steppe formation.

Coreidae Leach, 1815

Coreus marginatus (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material examined: 4 ♀♀, 27.08.2011 (locality 2), 1♂, 06.09.2011 (locality 1)

Habitat: Samples of the species were found at 1174 m in the cultural area dominated by cultural plants and trees.

Phyllomorpha lacerata (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)

Material examined: 1 ♀, 04.07.2012 (locality 1).

Habitat: Samples of the species were found on the grassy steppe in the *Pinus nigra* forest formation at a height of 1249 m.

***Syromastus rhombeus* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Material examined: 1 ♂, 22.06.2011; 1 ♀, 03.09.2011; 2 ♂♂, 06.07.2011 (locality 1); 2 ♀♀, 22.06.2011 (locality 2); 2 ♀♀, 25.06.2011 (locality 4); 3 ♀♀, 06.08.2012 (locality 10)

Habitat: Specimens were found in grass steppes, in areas with cultivated plants and in meadows at an altitude of 1249 m, 1174 m, 1450 m, and 1376 m.

***Centrocoris spiniger* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Material examined: 5♀♀, 21.06.2011; 1 ♂, 13.07.2011; 4♀♀, 27.08.2011; 4 ♂♂, 04.08.2012 (locality 1); 1♀, 10.07.2011 (locality 2); 5 ♂♂, 06.08.2012 (locality 10)

Habitat: Specimens were found in grassy steppe formation, between the *Pinus nigra* forest formation and the dominant vegetation in the region at an altitude of 1249 m, 1174 m, 1450 m and 1376 m.

***Centrocoris degener* (Puton, 1874)**

Material examined: 1 ♀, 05.09.2011 (locality 1)

Habitat: The specimen of the species was found on the grassy steppe at 1249 m in the region where the *Pinus nigra* formation is dominant.

***Coriomeris affinis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1839)**

Material examined: 2 ♂♂, 21.06.2011; 1 ♀, 26.06.2012 (locality 1); 3 ♀♀, 17.07.2011 (locality 2); 3 ♂♂, 25.06.2012 (locality 3); 1 ♂, 25.06.2011 (locality 5)

Habitat: Specimen belonging to the species were found at an altitude of 1249 m, 1174 m, 1548 m and 1347 m from the plants between the *Pinus nigra* forest formation, grassy steppe, the region where the crop plants dominate and the fields.

***Coriomeris subglaber* Horvath, 1917**

Material examined: 5 ♂♂, 22.06.2011 (locality 1)

Habitat: An example of this species was found on the grassy steppe in the region where *Pinus nigra* formation is dominant.

***Coriomeris denticulatus* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined: 2 ♀♀ 22.06.2011; 1 ♀, 06.07.2012 (locality 1); 3 ♂♂, 23.06.2011 (locality 2); 2♀♀, 25.06.2011 (locality 3); 2 ♂♂, 27.06.2011 (locality 7)

Habitat: Samples of the species were found at an altitude of 1249 m, 1174 m, 1347 m and 1382 m in the area of cultivated plants, plants between fields and gardens, grassy steppe and *Pinus nigra* forest formation.

***Loxocnemis dentator* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined: 1 ♀, 25.06.2012 (locality 3)

Habitat: Specimens were collected from the grassy steppe formation at an altitude of 1347 m.

***Ceraleptus gracilicornis* (Herrich-Schaeffer, 1835)**

Material examined: 2♂♂, 20.06.2011 (locality 1); 12 ♀♀ 5 ♂♂, 21.06.2011 (locality 2); 2 ♂♂, 25.06.2011 (locality 3); 4 ♀♀, 17.08.2011 (locality 6).

Habitat: Examples of this species were found at an altitude of 1249 m, 1174 m, 1347 m and 1507 m in the grassy steppe formation, the *Pinus nigra* forest area and the area dominated by culture plants.

Rhopalidae Amyot & Serville, 1843

***Stictopelurus pictus* (Fieber, 1861)**

Material examined: 1 ♂, 06.08.2012 (locality 10).

Habitat: An example of this species was found at an altitude of 1376 m in the region of grassy steppe formation, cultivated plants and cultivated areas.

***Corizus hyoscyami* (Linne, 1758)**

Material examined: 2♀♀ 1 ♂, 20.06.2012; 1 ♂, 05.08.2012 (locality 1); 2♀♀, 06.08.2012 (locality 10)

Habitat: Samples of the species were found on culture plants, *Pinus nigra* forest formation and grassy steppe at an altitude of 1249 m and 1376 m.

***Rhopalus parumpunctatus* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: 1♂, 05.07.2011; 1♀, 12.08.2011 (locality 1); 1♂, 03.08.2012 (locality 2); 1♂, 05.08.2012 (locality 9); 1♂, 06.08.2012 (locality 10)

Habitat: Samples of the species were found at 1249 m, 1174 m, 1074 m and 1376 m altitudes in the grassy steppe formation, *Pinus nigra* forest formation, cultivation area, reeds.

***Rhopalus subrufus* (Gmelin, 1788)**

Material examined: 1 ♀, 24.06.2011 (locality 2), 1♀, example, 04.07.2012 (locality 9), 1 ♂, 06.07.2012 (locality 10)

Habitat: The sample of the species was found at the 1174 m, 1074 m and 1376 m in the vegetation region and in the grassy steppe formation.

***Rhopalus conspersus* (Fieber, 1836)**

Material examined: 2♂♂, 21.06.2011 (locality 1), 1 ♀, 04.07.2012 (locality 9), 1 ♂, 06.07.2012 (locality 10)

Habitat: Specimens belonging to the species *Pinus nigra* forest, grassy steppe and cultural plants in the region, 1174 m, 1249 m and 1376 m was found.

***Maccevethus caucasicus* (Kolenati, 1845)**

?*Cimex lineola* Fabricius, 1787: 302. Junior primary homonym of *Cimex lineola* Linnaeus, 1758, *Cimex lineola*

Sulzer, 1776 and *Cimex lineola* Fabricius, 1781; synonymized by HORVATH (1901: 474).

= ?*Cimex sanctaetrucis* Gmelin, 1790: 2178. New name for *Cimex lineola* Fabricius, 1787.

= ?*Cimex lineolaris* Turton, 1802: 664. New name for *Cimex lineola* Fabricius, 1787.

= *Corizus caucasicus* Kolenati, 1845: 59 (syn. HORVÁTH 1901: 474).

= ?*Maccevethus lineola* var. *chobauti* Horváth, 1895: 155. Synonymized by JOSIFOV (1966: 61).

= *Stictopleurus elongatus* Blöte, 1934: 263. Synonymized by GÖLLNER-SCHIEDING (1975: 22).

= ?*Maccevethus lineola* var. *macedonica* Kormilev, 1936: 31, 39, 54. Synonymized by JOSIFOV (1966: 61, suspected).

= *Maccevethus houskai* Hoberlandt, 1952a: 15. Synonymized by JOSIFOV (1966: 61).

Remarks:

According to Kment & Banar (2010), misidentifications regarding the diagnosis of this taxon are given below.

HOBERLANDT 1956, *M. lineola* and *M. persicus* (my party, misidentification); SEIDENSTÜCKER 1964, *M. persicus* (misidentification); PUTSHKOV 1986; PEHLIVAN 1981, as *M. lutheri*; MOULET 1994, 1995; DOLLING 2006.

Material examined: 1♂ 2♀♀, 13.07.2011 (locality 1); 1 ♂, 13.08.2011 (locality 6); 1♀, 06.08.2012 (locality 10).

Habitat: Specimens belonging to the species were collected from 1249 m, 1507 m and 1376 m in the plants, grassy steppe and *Pinus nigra* forest formation between the fields.

***Maccevethus corsicus corsicus* Signoret, 1862**

Material examined: 1 ♀, 22.06.2011 (locality 1); 1 ♂, 26.06.2011 (locality 8); 1

♂, 06.08.2012 (locality 10).

Habitat: Specimens belonging to the species were found in the herbaceous steppe formation, the area where the culture plants are located, the cultivated area and the dominant plant species growing around the fields.

***Chorosoma schillingi* (Schilling, 1829)**

Material examined: 2♂♂, 23.06.2011, 2♀♀, 14.07.2011 (locality 1), 1♀, 25.06.2011 (locality 3), 1♀, 25.06.2011 (locality 4), 1♀, 26.06.2011 (locality 7), 1♂, 06.08.2012 (locality 10).

Habitat: Specimens were found at 1249 m, 1347 m, 1450 m, 1383 m and 1379 m heights in the dominant plant species between *Pinus nigra* forest formation, herbaceous steppe, cultivated areas and grain fields.

***Brachycarenum languidus* Horvath, 1891**

Material examined: 1♂, 03.08.2011 (locality 10)

Habitat: An example of this species was found on the *Pinus nigra* forest formation and grassy steppe at an altitude of 1249 m.

Stenocephalidae Dallas, 1892

***Dicranocephalus albipes* (Fabricius, 1781)**

Material examined: 1♂, 06.07.2012 (locality 10).

Habitat: An example of this species was found in the herbaceous steppe formation with culture plants.

CONCLUSION and DISCUSSION

159 specimens of Superfamily Coreoidea (Heteroptera) were collected from 10 different localities (in Yahyalı (Kayseri) and its vicinity between June-September

in 2011-2012 (Figure 1, Table 3).

After identified of the specimens were given in this study 24 species of 16 genera belonging to 4 families. The number of these taxons are; Alydidae, 2 genera, 4 species; Coreidae, 7 genera, 10 species; Rhopalidae, 6 genera, 9 species, and Stenocephalide, 1 genus, 1 species (Table 1, Figure.2).

According to literature reviews, only the records belonging to 17 species were found in the sources examined about Coreoidea superfamily in Kayseri province (Hoberlandt, 1955; Seidenstücker,1960; Tuatay, Kalkandelen, Aysev, 1971; Pehlivan, 1981; Altınayar, 1981; Kiyak,1990a). And below was given this records:

Alydidae: *Alydus calcaratus* (Linne, 1758), *Camptopus lateralis* (Germar, 1817), *Camptopus tragacanthae* (Kolenati, 1845); **Rhopalidae:** *Rhopalus parumpunctatus* (Schilling, 1829), *Maccevetthus caucasicus* (Kolenati, 1845) (=misidentification as *M. lineola* (Fb.,1787)), *Chorosoma schillingi* (Schilling, 1829), *Corizus brevicornis* Hv.,1917, *Liorrhysus hyalinus* (F.,1794), *Brachycarenum tigrinus* (Schl.,1829); *Stictopleurus crassicornis* (L.); **Coreidae:** *Haploprocta umbrina* Jak.,1883, *Enoplops disciger* (Klt.,1845), *Phyllomorpha laciniata* ssp. *laciniata* (Villers, 1789), *C. scabricornis* (Pz.,1809), *Centrocoris spiniger* (Fabr., 1781); **Stenocephalidae:** *D. agilis* ssp. *agilis* (Scop.,1763), *Dicranocephalus setulosus* (Fr.,1874).

Of them, identification of *M. lineola* (Fb.,1787) is mistake, was recorded from Kayseri-Hisarçık which is by Hoberlandt (1955) and by Tuatay, Kalkandelen, Aysev (1971).

This record is as *M. caucasicus* (Klt.,1862) assessable, and it's also distributed in Kayseri and in study area (Table 2).

As seen in the table, 24 species from this study and 17 species from previous studies are known from Kayseri fauna. Six of them found in this study were given also in previous studies. And 18 species are new records for the fauna of

Kayseri. As a result of these and previous studies, the total number of coreidae taxa from Kayseri is 35 species, which are 17 genera and 4 families.

On the other hand, 10 species found in previous studies were not encountered in this study. However, there are no records

given from Yahyalı district among the records of Kayseri province.

All species identified in the study are new records for the Heteroptera Fauna of Yahyalı.

Table 1. Genus and species number of Yahyalı (Prov. Kayseri) Coreoidea families

Families	Genus	Species
Alydidae	2	4
Coreidae	7	10
Rhopalidae	6	9
Stenocephalide	1	1

Figure 2. Distribution of species and genera numbers by families of Coreoidea in Study area.

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